

Influence of PET crystallinity on the mechanical behavior of CFRP composites at various temperature

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Introduction

❖ Carbon Fiber Reinforced Composites

- Light weight
- Low fuel consumption
- Corrosion resistance
- High specific strength and modulus

❖ Thermoplastic Composites

- High degree of chemical resistance
- Excellent damage and impact resistance
- Can be used over a wide range of temperature

❖ Purpose of this study

- In this study, the effect PET crystallinity on the mechanical properties at various temperature

Experimental

❖ CF/PET Composites manufacturing

Heating & Pressing process

- Temperature : 270 °C
- Dwelling time : 3min
- Pressure ≈ 10 bar

Cooling rate	
Fast cooling	100 °C/min
Slow cooling	2 °C/min

❖ Mechanical properties test

[Tensile test zig]

- Test method : ASTM D638
- Test speed : 2 mm/min
- Result : Tensile strength, Tensile modulus : $\Delta\sigma/\Delta\epsilon$
- Test method : ASTM D 3039
- Test speed : 2 mm/min
- Result : Tensile strength, Tensile modulus : $\Delta\sigma/\Delta\epsilon$

High temperature chamber

- Test method : ASTM D 3518
- Test speed : 2 mm/min
- Result : Shear strength, Shear modulus : $\Delta\tau/\Delta\gamma$

Results & Discussion

❖ DSC analysis of PET

❖ XRD analysis of PET

Percent crystallinity

$$X_c = \left[\frac{A_c}{A_a + A_c} \right] \times 100$$

❖ Mechanical properties with respect to the crystallinity of PET

- In plane shear property - ± 45° laminated composites

❖ SEM & optical microscope image analysis

Conclusion

- In this study, the influence of crystallinity on the mechanical behavior of CF/PET composites were demonstrated depending on the temperature conditions.
- In high temperature conditions, the high degree of crystallinity CF/PET composites showed much higher in-plane shear properties than that of low degree of crystallinity CF/PET composites.
- Also, the failure modes of the fractured CF/PET composites were changed respect to the crystallinity and the temperature condition.